

Terpenoids and Related Compounds: Part VII¹. Chemical Investigation of *Sapium eugeniaefolium* Ham.^{2,3}

H. N. Khastgir and B. P. Pradhan

Sapium eugeniaefolium is a glabrous tree available in tropical Himalayas from Kumaon at an altitude of 3000–4000 ft to Sikkim and in Assam at Goalpara and in Khasia hills.

The present authors have undertaken the chemical investigation of the bark of the plant which has not yet been examined chemically. From the benzene extract of the dried bark an insoluble yellow solid separated out which was collected by filtration. The filtrate containing the benzene soluble part was separated into neutral and acidic fractions. The neutral portion was chromatographed over alumina. The less polar fraction contained a mixture of compounds which after rechromatography over active alumina and crystallisation afforded taraxerone, m.p. 238–40°, $[\alpha]_D + 9^\circ$ and moretenone (I)^{4,5,6}, m.p. 200–202°, $[\alpha]_D + 50^\circ$, identified by m.m.p. and I.R. spectra. The more polar fractions provided taraxerol, m.p. 273–4°, $[\alpha]_D + 5^\circ$ and β -sitosterol m.p. 136°, identified as their acetates.

1. Part VI. H. N. Khastgir and S. N. Bose. Communicated.
2. J. D. Hooker, Flora of British India, Vol. V, p. 270; reprint 1954.
3. Cowan and Cowan, "The Trees of North Bengal", 1929, p. 119.
4. M. N. Galbraith, (the late) C. J. Meller, J. W. L. Rowson, E. Ritchie, J. S. Shannon, and W. C. Taylor, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1965, **18**, 226.
5. H. N. Khastgir, B. P. Pradhan, A. M. Duffield and L. J. Durham, *Chem. Comm.*, 1967, 1217.
6. Itiro Yosioka, Tsutomu Nakanishi and Isao Kitagawa, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1968, **12**, 1485.

EXPERIMENTAL*

Dried and powdered bark of *S. eugeniaefolium* (1 Kg) was extracted with benzene for 24 hrs. An insoluble yellow solid which separated out from the benzene extract was collected by filtration. The clear filtrate was concentrated and the gummy residue was taken up in ether. The ether extract was washed with 10% NaOH solution, water and then dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of ether gave a gummy residue (6 g) which was chromatographed over alumina (240 g) deactivated with 10% aq. acetic acid (9.6 ml). Petroleum eluted a second solid B (0.2 g), m.p. 240–55°. Further elution with petroleum : benzene (2 : 3) furnished a crystalline solid C (0.5 g), m.p. 130°.

Examination of solid A : Solid A which showed two spots on TLC was rechromatographed over active alumina (42 g). Elution with petroleum : benzene (4 : 1) gave a solid fraction I (0.3 g), m.p. 180–230° and solid fraction II (0.35 g), m.p. 190–95°.

Fraction I : Isolation of taraxerone : Fraction I above on repeated crystallisations from benzene and chloroform-methanol afforded a crystalline solid (TLC homogeneous), m.p. 238–40°, $[\alpha]_D + 9^\circ$ and was found to be identical with an authentic sample of taraxerone, (Lit.⁷ m.p. 240°, $[\alpha]_D + 12^\circ$). (Found C, 84.81; H, 11.23. Calc. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}$: C, 84.84; H, 11.39%). LAH reduction gave taraxerol, m.p. 276–7°, $[\alpha]_D + 3^\circ$, which on acetylation by acetic anhydride-pyridin method afforded taxaxeryl acetate, m.p. 297–8°, $[\alpha]_D + 7^\circ$, identical with an authentic sample (m.m.p.) (Lit.⁷ m.p. 304–5°, $[\alpha]_D + 9^\circ$).

Fraction II : Isolation of moretenone : Fraction II, m.p. 190–95° after repeated crystallisations from a mixture of chloroform and methanol afforded crystals of moretenone^{4'5'6} m.p. 198–200°, $[\alpha]_D + 50^\circ$, identical with an authentic specimen in all respects (m.m.p. and I.R.), $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 1705 cm^{-1} .

LAH reduction of moretenone : Isolation of 3-Epi-moretenol and Moretenol : Moretenone (0.5 g) in ether (50 ml) was treated with LAH (0.4 g) and refluxed for 4 hrs. On working up in the usual manner it gave a solid, m.p. 200–208° (0.45 g). The latter was chromatographed over deactivated alumina (25 g). Petroleum : benzene (4 : 1) eluted a solid, m.p. 220–2°, which after crystallisation from methanol gave crystals, m.p. 223–4°, $[\alpha]_D - 3^\circ$, identical in all respects with 3-epimoretenol (II)^{5'6} (Found : C, 84.36; H, 11.75. Calc. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$: C, 84.44; H, 11.81%). Further elution with petroleum : benzene (3 : 2) provided another solid, m.p. 220–24°, which after crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and methanol afforded moretenol (III)^{4'5'6} m.p. 228–230°, $[\alpha]_D + 24^\circ$ identical with an authentic sample of moretenol (m.m.p. and I.R.) (Found : C, 84.35; H, 11.10. Calc. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$: C, 84.44; H, 11.18%).

Solid B : Taraxerol : Solid B on crystallisation from benzene and chloroform-methanol mixture furnished taraxerol, m.p. 273–4°, $[\alpha]_D + 3.5^\circ$. The acetate prepared by pyridin-acetic anhydride method, had m.p. 295–7°, $[\alpha]_D + 11^\circ$ and was found to be identical in all

* All melting points are uncorrected. Petroleum used throughout the investigation has b.p. 60–80°. All rotations were taken in chloroform unless otherwise stated.

respects with taraxeryl acetate⁷. (Found C, 81.79; H, 11.20. Calc. for $C_{30}H_{52}O_2$: C, 81.99; H, 11.18%).

Solid C: β -sitosterol: Solid C on crystallisation from chloroform and methanol mixture furnished β -sitosterol, m.p. 136–7°, $[\alpha]_D -32^\circ$. The acetate, m.p. 126–7°, $[\alpha]_D -39^\circ$ was identical with an authentic specimen of β -sitosterol acetate. (Found: C, 81.59; H, 11.56. Calc. for $C_{31}H_{52}O_2$: C, 81.48; H, 11.50%).

The authors are indebted to Prof. J. N. Chatterjee, Patna Science College, Patna for I.R. spectra, to Dr. S. K. Sengupta, E.I.P.W., Calcutta for optical rotations and to Dr. P. Sengupta, University of Kalyani for authentic samples of taraxerone and taraxeryl acetate. One of us (B.P.) is grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of a Junior Research fellowship.

Department of Chemistry,
University of North Bengal,
Dist. Darjeeling.

Received June 10, 1968.